
2018 / 2nd Semester

PHARMACY

INTEGRATING PROFESSIONAL SKILL: FOOD

⊕ **Faculty of the discipline:** Prof. Dr. Victor Costa Castro-Alves

Description: PHARMACY Teaching Plan

Weekly workload: 08 hours

Total workload: 160

MENU

It comprises the stages of production, quality control and assurance, toxicological analysis, marketing and consumer guidance. It establishes the integration of content developed in the period with the food area, highlighting food safety, interactions with medicines and bioactive food compounds.

Enables the development of critical, ethical and normative sense of the Pharmacist's work in the Food area.

GENERAL OBJECTIVES

Develop the student's theoretical and practical skills to work as a pharmacist in the food sector, as described in the Brazilian Classification of Occupations. Integrate knowledge of chemistry and biochemistry of food components into food production processes. Establish a parallel between the practical activities of food analysis with normative aspects of the Pharmacist's performance, both in controlling and guaranteeing food quality.

Develop technical skills focused on food analysis and inspection, and enable students to provide guidance on interactions between foods and medicines. Present basic concepts about food safety, food preservation techniques, inspection, and updates on labeling in the food area. Stimulate the student's critical sense in relation to current topics associated with health and food, within the scope of the Pharmaceutical professional.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

* Encourage the student to integrate the concepts of chemistry and biochemistry with the composition and technology of food and food raw materials.

* Integrate practical and theoretical knowledge regarding the role of the Pharmacist in the areas of analysis, control, and quality assurance of food.

* Identify the role of microorganisms in the production and spoilage of food, as well as their relationship with human health.

* Introduce the student to the practical experience of professional Pharmacists in the food sector.

* Prepare the student for critical analysis of current topics related to food and health.

PROGRAM CONTENT

Basic concepts and practical aspects in chemistry, biochemistry and food analysis: introduction to food science, water in foods, proteins, carbohydrates (classification, properties, starch and dietary fiber), lipids, bioactive compounds in foods and functional foods, food labeling foods, normative aspects, and new approaches in assessing consumption and analyzing food matrices. Technology, production and health aspects of food: chemistry and biochemistry of foods of plant origin, fruit and vegetable processing and regulatory aspects, meat and fish technology, fermentative processes in food production, dairy product technology, food preservation,

microorganisms in food, and quality management in food production.

Practices: sampling, moisture and ash, protein determination, dietary fiber extraction, Maillard reaction, lipid determination, label evaluation, enzymatic hydrolysis of starch, determination of polyphenol oxidases, hamburger production, bakery products, casein precipitation, use of vegetable proteases, influence of preservatives in meat products.

TEACHING METHODS

Expository classes: theoretical content in the classroom using visual resources.

Use of continuous assessment and presentation of case studies. Inclusion of Project-Based Learning.

Practical classes: learning through experimentation.

EVALUATION METHODS

A **Procedural Assessment will be carried out**, consisting of different activities throughout the semester, and a **Final Assessment**.

- **Procedural assessment (10 points)**: will consist of (1) Continuous Assessments, (2) Module Assessments, (3) Project Development and (4) Progress Assessment.

(1) **Continuous assessments (3.0 points)**: assessments of theoretical content, reports and discussion of topics relevant to the content carried out during theoretical and practical classes. Work or assessments will be carried out using essay or multiple choice questions, with

consultation of bibliographic references. The average grade obtained in these activities will correspond to 3 points in the Procedural Assessment.

(2) **Module Assessments (2.0 points):** two written assessments throughout the course, consisting of essay and/or multiple choice questions, without consulting bibliographic references. The average of the two grades obtained in these activities will correspond to 2 points in the Procedural Assessment.

(3) **Project Development (3.0 points):** two team projects will be developed throughout the course. A script will be given to the students and each team must present the script and the case study described in the script. The average of the two grades obtained in these activities will correspond to 3 points in the Procedural Assessment.

(4) **Progress Assessment (2.0 points):** written, printed and unique assessment for all students on the course. There will be 4 multiple choice questions per semester, totaling 40 questions similar to those adopted in ENADE, competitions, among others. The grade obtained in the Progress Assessment will correspond to 2 points in the Procedural Assessment.

- **Final Assessment (10 points):** an assessment at the end of the course consisting of essay and/or multiple choice questions, without consulting bibliographic references.

In this way, the Final Average for each student will be calculated as follows:

Final Average = (Procedural Assessment Grade X 2) + (Final Assessment) X 3/5

The student will only be considered approved if the Final Average is equal to or greater than 6.0.

- **Substitute Assessment:** students who do not reach a final average equal to or greater than 6.0 may request a Substitute Assessment, which will also be individual and without consultation, following the same rules and covering the same content requested in the Final Assessment.

BASIC BIBLIOGRAPHY

DAMODARAN, S.; PARKIN, KL; FENNEMA, OR **Fennema Food Chemistry**. 4 ed. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2010. 900p.

GAVA, AJ; SILVA, CAB; FRIAS, JRG **Food technology: principles and applications**. 1.ed. São Paulo: Nobel, 2009. 511p

ALMEIDA-MURADIAN, LB, PENTEADO, MVC **Health surveillance: topics on legislation and food analysis**. 1 ed.Rio de Janeiro: Guanabara Koogan, 2007. 203p.

COMPLEMENTARY BIBLIOGRAPHY

ARAÚJO, JMA **Food chemistry: theory and practice**. 6. ed. Viçosa: UFV, 2015. 668p.

FORSYTHE, S. **Microbiology of food safety**. 2. Ed. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2013. 607p.

MIDIO, AF **Food toxicology**. 1.ed. Sao Paulo: Livraria Varela, 2000. 295p.

MORETTO, E.; FETT, R.; GONZAGA, L.V.; KUSKOSKI, IN **Introduction to food science**. Florianópolis: UFSC, 2002. 255p.

ORDÓÑEZ PEREDA, JA **Food technology: vol. 1: food components and processes**. 1.ed. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2007. 279p.

WEEKLY ACTIVITY SCHEDULE

MODULE I: Basic Concepts and Practical Aspects in Chemistry, Biochemistry and Analysis of food

1st Week – Presentation of the Module I Project; Introduction to food science; Water in foods: function and influences on food spoilage processes.

Practical Class: Sampling, humidity and ash. Project-Based Learning: presentation of the “MASTERCHEF” project.

2nd Week – Proteins in foods: chemistry, biochemistry, functional properties and analysis techniques.

Practical Class: Determination of proteins.

3rd Week – Carbohydrates – Classification and properties in foods.

Practical Class: Extraction of dietary fiber

4th Week – Carbohydrates – Starch and dietary fiber: influence on food texture and relationship with health.

Practical Class: Maillard Reaction

5th Week – Lipids: chemical and functional properties of foods.

Practical Class: Determination of lipids

6th Week – Bioactive compounds in foods and functional foods; Vitamins and Minerals.

Assessment: Module I

7th Week – Return Assessment of Module I; Food and novel labeling normative aspects: global trends.

Group work: Label evaluation

8th Week – New approaches to assessing consumption, techniques for analyzing food matrices and bioactive compounds.

Group work: Project-Based Learning. "MASTERCHEF".

9th Week - Finalization of the Module I Project

Case study: Seminars "Matilda Ho", "Sara Menker", "Birke Baher", "Carolyn Stell", "Pamela Ronald", among others (TED Talks)

MODULE II: Technology, Production and Sanitary Aspects of Food

10th Week – Presentation of the Module II Project; Chemistry and biochemistry of foods of plant origin.

Practical Class: Enzymatic hydrolysis of starch

11th Week – Fruit and vegetable processing and regulatory aspects.

Practical class: Determination of polyphenol oxidases

12th Week – Meat and fish technology and regulatory aspects.

Practical Class: Hamburger production

13th Week – Fermentation processes in food production.

Practical Class: Bread production

14th Week – Dairy product technology.

Practical Class: Casein precipitation

15th Week – Food preservation: conventional and unconventional methods; Quality management in the food industry.

Practical Class: Use of plant proteases

16th Week – Microbial diversity in foods; Foodborne microbial illnesses; Foodborne diseases.

17th Week – Role of the pharmacist in good food handling and production practices.

Assessment: Module II

18th week – Module II Feedback Assessment; Finalization of the Module II Project

Case study: Seminars “Rotten”, “Cooked” and “Explicando” (Netflix)

Practical Class: Influence of nitrates and nitrites on meat products

19th week – Final Assessment

20th week – Substitute Assessment